

Diazo Coupling of Metal Chelates of Benzoylacetone and Dibenzoylmethane

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The quasi-aromatic C_3O_2M ring system of metal chelates of benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane are known to undergo many electrophilic substitution reactions such as halogenation and nitration^{1,2}. It has been reported that the rate of substitution is slow when compared to metal acetylacetonates because of the steric effect of the bulky phenyl groups². In continuation of our studies on substitution reaction of aryldiazonium ion (a dominant electrophile) on metal 1,3-diketonates³, here we report the reaction of phenyldiazonium ion with Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} and Cr^{III} chelates of benzoylacetone (Hba) and dibenzoylmethane (Hdm).

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the diazo coupled products (Table 1) indicate that substitution has occurred on all the chelate rings of the metal 1,3-diketonates. Satisfactory results were also obtained by estimating the aniline formed during the reductive cleavage of the azo function using zinc and acetic acid⁴. Infrared spectra of the diazo coupled products of the Cr^{III} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} chelates are in accord with structure 1, while those of Cu^{II} with structure 2. Thus, absence of any absorption at $1600-1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectra of the former compounds indicate that both the carbonyl groups are involved in bonding with the metal ion as in metal 1,3-diketonates⁵. Apart from a strong band at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($C=C$), the spectra of the compounds display an intense band at $\sim 1545\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a medium intensity band at $\sim 1440\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be assigned³ respectively to the stretching of metal bonded carbonyl and $N=N$. Two medium intensity bands at ~ 450 and 320 cm^{-1} in the spectra can be assigned⁵ to ν_{M-O} . The ir spectra of the Cu^{II} chelates closely resemble that of the Cu^{II} chelates of the 1,2,3-triketone-2-phenylhydrazones reported earlier^{6,7}. Thus, characteristic bands due to the free benzoyl carbonyl ($\sim 1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$),

metal bonded carbonyl (1540 cm^{-1}), $C=N$ ($\sim 1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$), $M-N$ ($\sim 540\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $M-O$ ($\sim 430\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are all observed in the spectra, in agreement with structure 2 of the compounds.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF DIAZO COUPLED PRODUCTS

Diazo coupled product of	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	M
$Cu(ba)_2$	286	64.43	3.82	8.87	10.45
		(64.70)	4.38	9.44	10.70)
$Ni(ba)_2$	292	64.72	4.11	9.26	9.38
		(65.23)	4.42	9.53	9.97)
$Pd(ba)_2$	248	60.10	3.69	8.27	
		(60.34)	4.09	8.80)	
$Cr(ba)_3$	292	67.54	4.12	9.16	5.89
		(68.00)	2.60	9.92	6.14)
$Cu(dm)_2$	264	68.76	3.85	6.58	8.30
		(69.28)	4.12	7.70	8.76)
$Ni(dm)_2$	232	70.54	3.82	7.35	8.15
		(70.72)	2.21	7.86	8.24)
$Pd(dm)_2$	196	65.87	3.60	7.15	
		(66.28)	3.95	7.36)	
$Cr(dm)_3$	292	72.50	4.01	7.71	4.82
		(73.18)	4.35	8.13	5.03)

The absence of methylene proton signal (typical of metal 1,3-diketonates) in the 1H nmr spectra of the Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} chelates indicates that substitution has occurred on all the chelate rings. The integrated intensities of the alkyl ($\delta 2.50$) and aryl protons ($\delta 6.80-7.90$) are in agreement with the stoichiometry of the substitution products. That both the carbonyl groups are in the identical chemical environment is confirmed from the ^{13}C nmr spectra of the diazo coupled product of $Pd(dm)_2$ and $Ni(dm)_2$, which exhibit only a single carbonyl car-

bon signal at 196.58 and 197.10 ppm respectively. Thus, it appears that phenylazo substitution is possible in the case of metal chelates of benzoylacetone and dibenzylmethane similar to metal acetylacetonates and thenoyltrifluoroacetates³

Experimental

Cu(ba)₂, Ni(ba)₂, Pd(ba)₂, Cr(ba)₃, Cu(dm)₂, Ni(dm)₂, Pd(dm)₂ and Cr(dm)₃ were prepared and purified by reported methods¹. Phenyl diazonium chloride was obtained through the diazotisation of aniline using sodium nitrite and hydrochloric acid⁸. Excess nitrous acid present in the diazonium salt solution was destroyed

by adding urea. The coupling reaction was carried out as follows:

To a solution of the metal 1,3-diketonates (0.001 mol) in methanol (10 ml), kept below 5° in an ice-salt bath, was added slowly with vigorous stirring a cold aqueous solution of the diazonium salt (0.002 mol in the case of tris chelates 0.003 mol). A solution of NaOH (10⁻³ M) was used to maintain the pH of the mixture between 8 and 9. Stirring was continued for about 5 h while allowing the mixture slowly to attain room temperature. The precipitate formed was washed with water, sucked dry, recrystallised from hot ethanol and dried under reduced pressure (yield 20–30%). Infrared spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 435 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker WM 400 instrument.

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